

**STUDIES IN THE COTARNINE SERIES. PART IX.
ATTEMPTS TO SYNTHESISE ALKALOIDS
OF THE CRYPTOPINE TYPES.**

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The aim of the large variety of experiments which were undertaken under this caption was to effect the closure of a second isoquinoline ring on to that of cotarnine thus producing the skeleton of the structure of the molecules of the protopine and berberine alkaloids. Some of the results are now recorded. It would be seen that although, as a rule, the reactions proceeded smoothly in the beginning, attempts at ring-closure at the final stage have hitherto been unsuccessful.

Cotartine was condensed with *o*-toluoyl chloride (b.p. 213°/760 mm.) to *o*-toluoylcotarnine, m.p. 99-100° (I) which was obtained in excellent yield and which showed the presence of a free and reactive aldehyde group by the formation of a crystalline oxime (m.p. 170°), semicarbazone (m.p. 200°) and hydrazone (m. p. 211°).

Although, assuming structure (I) to be correct, the relative orientation of the methyl and the aldehyde groups would make the prospect of interaction between them seem reasonably certain, our expectations were not realised and all attempts in the direction of closing the ring (II) ended in failures. Different condensing agents, *e.g.*, dilute alkalis, sodium ethoxide, HCl gas, phosphorus pentachloride, phosphorus oxychloride, etc., were tried but they led in almost all cases to the recovery of unchanged materials at the end. Proceeding next with the assumption that the methyl hydrogen atoms required to be activated, *e.g.*, by the introduction of a halogen atom or a CN-group or a nitro-group, bromotoluoyl bromide,

o-cyano-*o*-toluoyl chloride and *p*-nitro-*o*-toluoyl chloride (3-nitro-6-methylbenzoyl chloride) were prepared, the first by the bromination of *o*-toluoyl chloride according to the process described by Davis and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2202), the second from phthalide and potassium cyanide, and the third from *p*-nitro-*o*-toluidine through the nitrile and the acid. The interaction of cotarine with these compounds was tried under different conditions. The first two gave unstable oily products which were readily decomposed into cotarine on attempting to condense them in the presence of alkalis or dehydrating agents. *p*-Nitro-*o*-toluoyl cotarine was, however, obtained easily as crystals (m.p. 125°), which formed a crystalline oxime and semicarbazone indicating the presence of a free aldehyde group, but all efforts to condense it to the desired ring structure proved fruitless.

In further continuation of this work, it seemed desirable to investigate the possibility of closing a second isoquinoline ring on to that of cotarine by condensing the latter base with compounds containing a reactive methylene group, in the presence of acetic anhydride. Some of the experiments carried out with this end in view are described briefly in this paper, attempts being made to condense cotarine with homo-phthalonitrile, phthalide, nitrophthalide, meconine and nitromeconine. Dutt and Seshacharyulu (*Proc. U. P. Acad. Sci.*, 1934, 4, 159) have studied the condensation of cotarine with several compounds containing a reactive methylene group such as hippuric acid, benzyl cyanide, phthalide, etc., under similar conditions. On the assumption that in the presence of acetic anhydride, the secondary base gets instantly acetylated, thus preventing the imino-group from taking part in the condensation and leaving the aldehyde group alone free to react, as in a Claisen's or a Knoevenagel's reaction, the following constitution has been assigned to the condensation products:—

The condensation of cotarine with homo-phthalonitrile (V) in the presence of acetic anhydride gave a compound, m.p. 245°, insoluble in dilute acids and slowly dissolving in dilute sodium hydroxide. The results of analysis of this compound were found to be in agreement with those

required for the acetyl derivative of homo-phthalonitrile (VII) and not the expected "anhydroacetylcotarnino-homo-phthalonitrile" (VIII).

The identity of the compound formed in this reaction with (VII) was also proved by (i) hydrolysing it with dilute hydrochloric acid when homo-phthalic acid (m.p. 180°) was obtained, and (ii) by synthesis from homo-phthalonitrile by the action of acetic anhydride (*vide supra*).

5-Nitrophthalide, on the other hand, was found to condense with cotarnine in the presence of acetic anhydride yielding the expected 'anhydroacetylcotarnino-5-nitrophthalide' (IX) melting at 165° , insoluble in dilute acids and slowly dissolving in sodium hydroxide.

It was expected that the acid (X), obtained from the compound by treatment with hot alkali, should be capable of being deacetylated with dilute acids, thus making the closure of a second isoquinoline ring possible :

Deacetylation with warm dilute hydrochloric acid resulted in a clear solution from which on basification only cotarnine could be recovered.

It has to be recorded here that all attempts to prepare 5-nitro-homophthalonitrile were unsuccessful. The nitrile could be prepared neither by fusing a mixture of 5-nitrophthalide and potassium cyanide as in the preparation of homo-phthalonitrile, nor by refluxing a mixture of 5-nitrophthalide and alcoholic potassium cyanide; complete decomposition took place in the former case, while in the latter the original product was recovered unchanged.

It was further noted that the expected condensations could not be carried out either with phthalide or meconine by heating with acetic anhydride (Dutt and Seshacharyulu, *loc. cit.*). From phthalide was obtained a compound (m. p. 196-98°), slowly dissolving in sodium

carbonate, which on recrystallisation from alcohol, melted at 201° , and was identified as anhydroacetylcotarninoacetic acid, m. p. 201° , by a mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of the latter. It is to be observed that in these cases, no condensation took place, acetic anhydride reacting alone with cotarnine and yielding anhydroacetylcotarninoacetic acid. Dutt's conclusion, therefore, that the product with phthalide was anhydroacetylcotarninophthalide could not be confirmed.

Lastly attention was directed to the possibilities of synthesising compounds in which the reactive NH_2 -group would replace the methylene radicle, the subsequent reaction between the aldehyde and the amino groups being expected to result in the formation of cyclic structure resembling those of the protopine alkaloids but differing from the latter in having a nitrogen atom in place of methine group. Acetyl anthranilic acid from the oxidation of aceto-*o*-toluidide and its chloride were first employed for this purpose, but the chloride was found to decompose rather rapidly under the conditions necessary for a Schotten-Baumann reaction, and later methyl anthranilate was used instead. The condensation of the latter with cotarnine proceeded smoothly, the product being anhydrocotarnine-methylanthranilate, m. p. 136° , having the following probable structure (XII) :

(XII)

(XIII)

The proximity of the secondary imino-group and the carbonmethoxy group encourages the hope that the removal of a molecule of methyl acetate by the action of such dehydrating agents as acetic anhydride, etc., would not present insuperable difficulties. Experiments which are being conducted in this field have not concluded yet.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

o-Toluoylcotarnine (I).—Cotarnine was suspended in 2*N*-sodium hydroxide, the required amount of freshly prepared *o*-toluoyl chloride was added and vigorously shaken when a thick oil resulted. The oil was washed well with water containing a little hydrochloric acid and then rubbed with ligroin, when the unreacted toluoyl chloride was removed and the oil gradually solidified. Crystallisation from dilute alcohol (1 : 1) furnished a colourless solid, m.p. 99-100°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 3.7. $C_{20}H_{21}O_5N$ requires N, 3.94 per cent).

The *Oxime*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised in bunches of flat needles, m.p. 170°. It is readily soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide and is reprecipitated unchanged on acidification. (Found : N, 7.41. $C_{20}H_{23}O_5N_2$ requires N, 7.56 per cent).

The *Semicarbazone* crystallised in needles, m.p. 200°, and the *hydrazone*, in soft needles, m.p. 211°.

p-Nitro-*o*-toluoylcotarnine.—*p*-Nitro-*o*-tolunitrile (Ber., 1898, 31, 2880) was obtained in long yellow felted needles, m.p. 105°, by diazotising a suspension of finely divided *p*-nitro-*o*-toluidine hydrochloride, decomposing with potassium cuprocyanide at 70° in the usual way and purifying the product by a process of slow sublimation, yield 3.5 g. of the pure crystals from 10 g. of the toluidine. *p*-Nitro-*o*-toluic acid (colourless crystals, m.p. 179°) was obtained in quantitative yield by the hydrolysis of the nitrile with 50% sulphuric acid, and the chloride (colourless crystals, m.p. 59°) was prepared in the usual way by heating with thionyl chloride.

Cotarnine (2 g.) was suspended in 2*N*-sodium hydroxide, the required amount of *p*-nitro-*o*-toluoyl chloride dissolved in toluene was added and shaken well. After leaving for 30 minutes, the upper toluene layer was separated, washed once with water and allowed to evaporate spontaneously. The resulting oil was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid in order to remove any of the unreacted cotarnine and rubbed with rectified spirit, when it changed rapidly into a gritty solid. Crystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol gave beady crystals, m.p. 124-25°. The compound is insoluble in dilute acids and alkali. (Found : C, 60.5 ; H, 5.2 ; N, 7.15. $C_{20}H_{20}O_7N_2$ requires C, 60.0 ; H, 5.0 ; N, 7.0 per cent).

The *Semicarbazone*, prepared by the usual method, crystallised in short yellow square plates, m.p. 219-20°. (Found : N, 15.21. $C_{21}H_{23}O_7N_5$ requires N, 15.31 per cent).

The *Oxime* crystallised in beady crystals, m.p. 175° and the *hydrazone* formed thin square plates, m.p. 255° .

The following attempts were made for ring-closure : (a) *Sodium ethoxide* : The compound was dissolved in warm absolute alcohol, a few c.c. of sodium ethoxide added and left overnight. (b) *Piperidine* : A few drops of piperidine were added to an alcoholic solution of the substance and kept for 24 hours at 40° - 50° . (c) *Dry HCl gas* : The alcoholic solution was saturated with the gas and left for 2 days. (d) *Concentrated sulphuric acid* : The substance was dissolved in ice-cold concentrated sulphuric acid, the solution left in the ice chamber for 12 hours and then poured into water. (e) *Sodium hydroxide* : 1 c.c. of dilute caustic soda was added to an alcoholic solution of the substance and left for 2 days. In all cases the original compounds were recovered unchanged.

Action of Acetic Anhydride on Homo-phthalonitrile (VII).—Homo-phthalonitrile (1 g.) was heated under reflux with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) for 1 hour. On cooling, crystalline solid separated, which was filtered, washed well with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as a crystalline solid, m.p. 245° . It is insoluble in dilute acids and slowly dissolves in alkali and can not be reprecipitated from the alkaline solution. (Found : N, 6.7. $C_{11}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 6.9 per cent).

Anhydroacetylcotarnino-5-nitrophthalide (IX).—Cotarnine (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and 5-nitrophthalide (0.8 g.) were refluxed for 1 hour and poured into water when a thick oil was obtained. It was washed well with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in orange coloured needles, m.p. 165° . It is insoluble in dilute acids. (Found : N, 6.36. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.36 per cent).

Anhydrocotarnino-methyl anthranilate (XII).—Cotarnine (1 g.) was rubbed with methyl anthranilate (0.64 g.) and left overnight. The hard, light yellow crystalline solid was washed and crystallised from boiling alcohol as colourless crystals, m.p. 136° . It dissolves in cold dilute acids and is reprecipitated on basification. On treatment with acetic anhydride, it decomposes into cotarnine and the acetyl derivative of methyl anthranilate. (Found : N, 7.3. $C_{20}H_{22}O_5N_2$ requires N, 7.56 per cent).